

Forced Degradation Studies, Method Development and Validation Of RP-HPLC Method For the Analysis of Plecanatide in Bulk and Tablet Dosage Form

Dharani C.^{1*}, Vetrichelvan T.², Murugan S.³

¹M. Pharm Student, ²HOD cum Dean Research, ³Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Adhiparasakthi College of Pharmacy, Melmaruvathur-603319, Tamil Nadu, Affiliated to The Tamil Nadu Dr. M. G. R. Medical University, Chennai-600 032, India

ABSTRACT

Objective: To develop and validate a novel, simple, accurate, precise, and stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Plecanatide in bulk and tablet formulation, including forced degradation studies. **Methods:** The chromatographic separation was achieved using a C18 column (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm) with a mobile phase consisting of water and acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) with 0.05% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min, with UV detection at 204 nm. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines for linearity, precision, accuracy, ruggedness, robustness, LOD, and LOQ. Forced degradation studies were conducted under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, reductive, thermal, photolytic, and UV light conditions to evaluate the stability-indicating nature of the method. **Results:** Plecanatide showed a sharp and symmetric peak with a retention time of 3.092 minutes. The method was linear in the concentration range of 6-30 μg/mL with a correlation coefficient ($r^2 = 0.9999$). Precision results (% (RSD)) were below 2%, and recovery values ranged from 99.55% to 101.00%, confirming accuracy. LOD and LOQ were found to be 0.7324 μg/mL and 2.2195 μg/mL, respectively. Forced degradation studies indicated significant degradation under acidic and reduction conditions, while the drug was relatively stable under alkaline, oxidation, photolytic, thermal, and UV light stress. **Conclusion:** The developed RP-HPLC method is simple, precise, accurate, and stability-indicating. It is suitable for routine quality control, stability testing, and degradation behavior studies of Plecanatide in bulk and tablet dosage form.

Keywords: RP-HPLC, validation, forced degradation, ICH guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Plecanatide is a synthetic analogue of uroguanylin and acts as a guanylate cyclase-C (GC-C) agonist. It is primarily prescribed for the management of Chronic Idiopathic Constipation (CIC) and Irritable Bowel Syndrome with Constipation (IBS-C). The drug was first developed in 2007 and subsequently approved by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in January 2017 for adult CIC, followed by its approval in 2018 for IBS-C. Both CIC and IBS-C are functional gastrointestinal disorders with a significant prevalence in the United States, affecting approximately 12% and 10–14% of the population, respectively [1].

Plecanatide, chemically designated as (2S)–2-[(1R, 4S, 7S, 10S, 13S, 16R, 19S, 22S, 25R, 32S, 38R)-10-(2-amino-2-oxoethyl)-25-[(2S)-4-carboxy-2-[(2S)-3-carboxy-2-[(2S)-2,4-diamino-4-oxobutanoyl]amino]propanoyl]amino]butanoyl]amino]-22-(2-carboxyethyl)-32-[(1R)-1-hydroxyethyl]-4-methyl-19-(2-methylpropyl)-3,6,9,12,15,18,21,24,30,33,36-undecaoxo-7,13-di(propan-2-yl)-27,28,40,41-tetrathia-2,5,8,11,14,17,20,23,31,34,37-undecazabicyclo[14.13.13]dotetracontane-38-carbonyl]amino]-4-methylpentanoic acid [2, 3] (Figure. 1), with a molecular formula of C₆₅H₁₀₄N₁₈O₂₆S₄ and molecular weight of 1682 Daltons [4].

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Plecanatide

Due to its clinical importance and growing therapeutic use, the development of accurate, sensitive, and validated analytical methods for the estimation of plecanatide is essential. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) has emerged as a widely accepted technique for drug analysis because of its high resolution, reproducibility, and reliability in Pharmaceutical quality control. Analytical methods also play a crucial role in stability studies, including forced degradation studies, which are recommended by ICH guidelines to evaluate the chemical stability of drug substances under stress conditions. Such studies ensure drug safety, efficacy, and quality throughout its shelf life. Determining the percentage degradation under different stress conditions ensures that the method is stability-indicating and suitable for regulatory applications [5, 6].

The present work focuses on the development and validation of a simple, precise, accurate, and stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for the quantitative estimation of Plecanatide in bulk and tablet dosage form, along with forced degradation studies as per ICH norms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentation

The analysis was carried out using a Shimadzu HPLC system equipped with an LC-20AD, a UV-Visible detector, and Lab Solutions software, employing a Shimadzu C₁₈ column (250 mm × 4.5, 5 μm). An electronic balance (Shimadzu AUX-220) was used for weighing, while sample sonication was performed using a Sonicator. A hot air oven (InfraDIGI, up to

250 °C) and a UV light chamber were utilized for stability and degradation studies.

Reagents and Chemicals

All chemicals and reagents used were of HPLC grade and procured from Qualigens India Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. Pure plecanatide was kindly supplied by a Pharmaceutical company in Telangana, India, while Plectide® tablets (containing 3 mg of plecanatide per tablet) were obtained from a local Pharmacy. The solvents and reagents employed included HPLC grade water, HPLC grade acetonitrile, 0.05 % trifluoroacetic acid, 0.1 N hydrochloric acid, 3 % hydrogen peroxide, 10 % sodium bisulfate, and 0.1 N sodium hydroxide.

METHOD OPTIMIZATION

The chromatographic method was optimized by systematically varying different parameters, including mobile phase composition, detection wavelength, diluent and flow rate, to achieve sharp, symmetric peaks with suitable retention time and resolution.

Mobile phase Optimization

Various combinations of water, methanol, and acetonitrile, with and without acidic modifiers, were tested. Mobile phase without modifiers resulted in peak broadening and tailing. The inclusion of 0.05 % trifluoroacetic acid (TFA) significantly improved peak symmetry and reproducibility. The final optimized mobile phase consisted of water and acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) with 0.05 % TFA, which produced sharp, symmetric peaks with an acceptable retention time.

Selection of Diluent

The mobile phase [water: acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) with 0.05 % TFA] was selected as the diluent to ensure complete solubility, compatibility, and reproducible chromatographic performance.

Selection of Wavelength

The UV spectrum of plecanatide was recorded in the range of 200–400 nm. The drug exhibited maximum absorbance at 204 nm, which was selected as the detection wavelength since it provided maximum sensitivity.

Optimization of Flow Rate

Flow rates in the range of 0.5–1.0 mL/min were evaluated. At higher flow rates, resolution decreased, while at lower flow rates, analysis time was prolonged. A flow rate of 0.8 mL/min was found to provide a balance between resolution and analysis time and was selected as optimal.

Final Optimized Condition

The optimized chromatographic conditions included a Shimadzu C₁₈ column (250 mm × 4.5, 5 µm), a mobile phase of water: acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) with 0.05 % TFA, flow rate of 0.8 mL/min, UV detection at 204 nm, and an injection volume of 20 µL. These conditions produced sharp, symmetric peaks with acceptable system suitability parameters, fulfilling ICH requirements.

Analytical Method Development

Preparation of Mobile Phase

The mobile phase was prepared by mixing water and acetonitrile in the ratio of 50:50 (v/v) with 0.05 % TFA, filtered through a 0.45 µm membrane filter, and degassed by sonication before use.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

An accurately weighed quantity of plecanatide (30 mg) was transferred into a 50 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in diluent, and diluted to the mark. This resulted in a stock solution with a concentration of 600 µg/mL.

Preparation of working standard solution

From the standard stock solution, pipetted out 5 mL into a 25 mL volumetric flask and diluted to volume with the diluent to obtain a working standard solution of 120 µg/mL.

Preparation of sample solution

Twenty tablets were weighed to determine the average weight and then finely powdered. A portion of the powder equivalent to 3 mg of plecanatide was transferred into a 25 mL volumetric flask containing 15 mL of the mobile phase, sonicated for 15 minutes, and allowed to stand at room temperature for 5 minutes. The solution was then diluted to volume with

the mobile phase to obtain a sample stock solution of 120 µg/mL, which was filtered through Whatman filter paper. From this sample stock solution, pipetted out 1 mL was transferred into a 10 mL volumetric flask and diluted to volume with the mobile phase to yield a concentration of 12 µg/mL.

METHOD VALIDATION

System Suitability

System suitability was assessed by injecting the standard solution under optimized conditions. Plecanatide produced a sharp, symmetric peak at 3.092 min. Theoretical plates were >2000, and the tailing factor was <2.0. These values indicate good column efficiency and peak symmetry. All parameters complied with ICH acceptance criteria.

Linearity

For the linearity study, aliquots of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 mL of the working standard solution (120 µg/mL) were each transferred into separate 10 mL volumetric flasks and diluted to volume with the diluent to obtain concentrations of 6-30 µg/mL. Each solution was injected, and calibration curves were constructed by plotting peak area against concentration.

Precision

The precision of the developed method was evaluated by analysing a sample solution of plecanatide (12 µg/mL) six times within the same day, and the % RSD of the peak area was calculated.

Accuracy

Accuracy was evaluated by standard-addition method at three concentration levels: 50 %, 100 %, and 150 % of the target concentration. Pre-analyzed tablet powder equivalent to 3 mg of plecanatide was spiked with known amounts of standard drug and analyzed in triplicate.

Robustness

The robustness of the developed HPLC method was evaluated by introducing deliberate, minor variations in the chromatographic conditions and observing their effect on system suitability parameters. The following

parameters were altered one at a time, and the sample solution was injected in triplicate for each condition:

i) **Mobile phase composition:** The ratio of water and acetonitrile (50:50, v/v) containing 0.05 % TFA was varied by ± 1.0 mL (49:51 v/v and 51:49 v/v).

ii) **Detection wavelength:** The wavelength was varied by ± 1 nm (203 nm and 205 nm).

iii) **Flow rate:** The flow rate was varied by ± 0.1 mL/min (0.7 mL/min and 0.9 mL/min).

For each condition, the % RSD of the mean peak area was calculated. The results indicated no significant changes in retention time, peak symmetry, or system suitability parameters, confirming that the method is robust.

Ruggedness

Ruggedness of the proposed method was evaluated by analyzing a plecanatide sample solution (12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) using two different analysts and two different instruments under the same operational and environmental conditions.

LOD & LOQ

LOD and LOQ were calculated in accordance with ICH guidelines using the standard deviation (σ) of the y-intercept and the slope (s) of the calibration curve:

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / s$$

Where:

σ = the standard deviation of the response

s = the slope of the calibration curve

Forced Degradation Studies

Forced degradation studies were performed to assess the stability of Plecanatide under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, reductive, thermal, photolytic, and UV light conditions. The drug was analyzed using a validated RP-HPLC method, and the extent of degradation was quantified as the percentage of drug remaining. These studies demonstrated that Plecanatide is stable under most stress conditions, with measurable degradation observed only under

specific conditions, confirming the method's stability-indicating capability.

Acid degradation ^[7]

From the 120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ plecanatide working standard solution, pipetted out 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask. To this, 1 mL of 0.1 N HCl was added and the mixture was kept for 24 hours. The solution was then neutralized with 1 mL of 0.1 N NaOH, diluted to volume with diluent, and injected into the HPLC system. Chromatogram was recorded to observe any changes occurring during the stress period.

Alkali degradation ^[7]

From the 120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ plecanatide working standard solution, pipetted out 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask. To this, 1 mL of 0.1 N NaOH was added and the solution was allowed to stand for 24 hours. It was then neutralized with 1 mL of 0.1 N HCl, diluted to the mark with diluent, and analyzed by HPLC.

Oxidative degradation ^[7]

From the 120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ plecanatide working standard solution, pipetted out 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask. To this, 1 mL of 3 % hydrogen peroxide solution was added, and the mixture was kept for 24 hours. The volume was made up with diluent and analyzed by HPLC to monitor oxidative degradation.

Reduction degradation ^[8]

From the 120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ plecanatide working standard solution, pipetted out 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask. To this, 1 mL of 10 % sodium bisulfate solution was added and kept for 24 hours. The volume was then made up with diluent and injected into the HPLC system.

Photolytic degradation ^[9]

Plecanatide raw material was exposed to direct sunlight for 4 hours. From the standard, a 120 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ solution was prepared in diluent, pipetted out 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask, diluted to volume with diluent, and analyzed by HPLC to assess photolytic degradation.

Thermal degradation ^[9]

Weighed required quantity of plecanatide and subjected to thermal degradation by keeping it in a hot air oven at 70 °C for 24 hours. From the standard, a 120 µg/mL solution was prepared using diluent, pipetted out 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask, diluted to volume with diluent, and injected into the HPLC system to monitor thermal degradation.

UV degradation ^[9]

Plecanatide raw material was exposed to UV light for 24 hours. After exposure, a 120 µg/mL solution was prepared with diluent, pipetted out 1 mL into a 10 mL volumetric flask, diluted to volume with diluent, and

injected into the HPLC system to monitor degradation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Method development and optimization

The HPLC procedure was optimized to develop a suitable method for the determination of Plecanatide. Initially, different ratios of methanol, acetonitrile, and water were tested as mobile phases. Based on peak shape and resolution, a combination of water and acetonitrile was selected for further optimizations that are given in **Table 1**.

Table 1: The different ratios of mobile phase tried and remark on obtained peaks

S. No	Mobile phase composition	Flow rate	Interference
1	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (40:30:30 v/v/v)	1 ml/min	Peak showed slight tailing, early elution and baseline noise observed
2	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (60:25:15 v/v/v)	1 ml/min	Peak can be splitted, early elution and baseline noise observed
3	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (60:25:15 v/v/v)	0.6 ml/min	Early elution and baseline noise observed
4	Water: methanol: acetonitrile (20:40:40 v/v/v)	1 ml/min	Peak showed tailing and baseline noise observed
5	Water: methanol (80:20 v/v)	1 ml/min	Retention time is acceptable, but resolution can be improved
6	Water: acetonitrile (50:50 v/v)	0.5 ml/min	Peak showed fronting with minimal baseline noise
7	Water: acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) with 0.05 % trifluoro acetic acid (Optimized chromatogram)	0.8 ml/min	Peak showed good symmetry and acceptable retention time

The optimized chromatogram for plecanatide are shown in **Figure 2** (blank) and **Figure 3** (optimized chromatogram)

Figure 2: Chromatogram for Blank

Figure 3: Optimized chromatogram for Standard

Method Validation

The developed HPLC method for Plecanatide was validated as per ICH guidelines.

System suitability

System suitability and chromatographic parameters, including tailing factor and theoretical plates, were evaluated, and the results are given in Table 2.

Table 2: System suitability parameters of plecanatide

Parameters	Results
Number of theoretical plates or efficacy	3516
Tailing factor	0.567
Retention time	3.092
Peak area	371042

Linearity

The method showed excellent linearity with the regression equation $y = mx + c$ and a correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.9999$), confirming its suitability for quantitative analysis. The data are given in Table 3. Calibration curves were constructed in the

concentration range of 6-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ is shown in figure 4. The optical parameters, including correlation coefficient, slope, intercept, LOD, and LOQ, are given in Table 4.

Table 3: Linearity data for plecanatide

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Peak Area
6	179889
12	371493
18	550013
24	729909
30	910031

Figure 4: Calibration curve for plecanatide

Table 4: Optical parameters and linearity data of Plecanatide

Parameters	Plecanatide
Beer's law ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	6 - 30
Regression equation ($y=mx + c$)	$Y = 30375x + 1265.2$
Slope	30375
Intercept	1265.2
Correlation coefficient (r^2)	0.9999
Standard error	2752.3
Limit of detection ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.7324
Limit of quantification ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	2.2195

Precision

System precision was assessed by six replicate injections of 12 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ plecanatide. The % RSD of

0.0395 was within acceptable limits, confirming the method's precision (Table 5, Figure 5).

Table-5: Precision of Plecanatide Formulation

Precision	Label claim	Amount found (mg/tab)	% purity	Average %	S. D	%RSD
1	3 mg	3.0151	100.50	100.52	0.0398	0.0395
2		3.0173	100.57			
3		3.0154	100.51			
4		3.0157	100.52			

5		3.0176	100.58			
6		3.0145	100.48			

Figure 5: Precision chromatogram for plecanatide

Accuracy

Accuracy was evaluated by the standard addition method at three concentration levels, each analyzed in triplicate. The mean % recovery of plecanatide was within acceptable limits, confirming the accuracy of the proposed method (Table 6).

Table-6: Accuracy (recovery) data for Plecanatide

Sample	% Conc	Sample amount (µg/ml)	Amount spiked (µg/ml)	Estimated amount (µg/ml) *	Recovered amount (µg/ml) *	Average % Recovery *	SD	%RSD
PLE	50	12	6	18.06	6.06	101.00	0.0923	0.0913
	100	12	12	23.98	11.98	99.83	0.0461	0.0461
	150	12	18	29.92	17.92	99.55	0.0818	0.0821

* Mean of 3 Observations

Robustness

Robustness was assessed by making deliberate variations in flow rate (± 0.1 mL/min), wavelength (\pm

1 nm), and mobile phase composition (± 1 mL). The % RSD values remained within acceptable limits, demonstrating that the method is robust. The robustness results are given in Table 7.

Table-7: Robustness data for Plecanatide

PARAMETER	AMOUNT FOUND * (mg/tab)	% PURITY *	SD	% RSD
FLOW RATE				
0.7 ml/min	3.0267	100.89	0.6025	0.5971
0.8 ml/min	3.0257	100.85	0.4895	0.4853
0.9 ml/min	3.0261	100.87	0.6229	0.6175
WAVELENGTH				
203 nm	3.0216	100.72	0.4603	0.4570
204 nm	3.0358	101.19	0.4611	0.4556
205 nm	3.0102	100.34	0.6425	0.6403
MOBILE PHASE COMPOSITION				
Water: Acetonitrile 51:49 (0.05 % TFA)	3.0165	100.55	0.0513	0.0510
Water: Acetonitrile 50:50 (0.05 % TFA)	3.0283	100.94	0.5565	0.5513
Water: Acetonitrile 49:51(0.05 % TFA)	3.0251	100.83	0.6446	0.6392

* Mean of 3 Observations

Ruggedness

Ruggedness was evaluated under varied conditions, with % RSD values within acceptable limits,

confirming good reproducibility. The results are given in Table 8.

Table-8: Ruggedness data for Plecanatide

Sample	Condition	% obtained	S. D	% RSD
PLE	Analyst-1	101.19	0.6071	0.5946
	Analyst-2	100.85	0.4842	0.4801
	Instrument-1	100.54	0.0642	0.0638
	Instrument-2	100.83	0.5031	0.4989

*** Mean of 3 Observations****Forced degradation studies**

Forced degradation studies were carried out to evaluate the stability of plecanatide under different stress conditions. The drug showed notable degradation in acidic and reductive environments, whereas it was stable under alkaline, oxidative,

photolytic, UV, and thermal conditions. These findings demonstrate that the developed RP-HPLC method is capable of detecting degradation and can be considered stability-indicating. The results are given in **Table 9** and the chromatograms are shown in Figures 6-12.

Table 9: Degradation data for plecanatide

Stress conditions	Time interval	% degradation
Acid degradation	24 hrs	18.91
Alkali degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Oxidative degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
Reduction degradation	24 hrs	23.18
Photolytic degradation	4 hrs	Not degraded
Thermal degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded
UV degradation	24 hrs	Not degraded

Figure 8: Chromatogram for Oxidative degradation study

Figure 11: Chromatogram for Thermal degradation study

Figure 9: Chromatogram for Reduction degradation study

Figure 12: Chromatogram for UV light degradation study

Figure 10: Chromatogram for Photolytic degradation study

Table 10: Comparative studies with reported analytical methods

S. No	Parameters	Developed Method	Reported Method for RP-HPLC-UV ^[10]	Reported Method for RP-HPLC-UV ^[11]
1	Mobile Phase	Water: Acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) with 0.05 % TFA	2 ml Ortho phosphoric acid, 2 ml Triethylamine in HPLC Water: Methanol [520: 480 v/v]	Acetonitrile: Water (65:35 v/v)
2	Retention time	3.092 mins	4.543 mins	3.4 mins

3	Linearity and Range	$r^2 = 0.9999$ 6-30 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	$r^2 = 0.9999$ 10-60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	$r^2 = 0.9997$ 10-60 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
4	Precision	% RSD = 0.0395	% RSD System precision = 0.18	% RSD Intraday = 1.20
			Method precision = 0.15	Interday = 0.19
5	Accuracy	% RSD 50 % = 0.0913 100 % = 0.0461 150 % = 0.0821	% RSD = 0.18	% RSD 80 % = 10.7326 100 % = 7.2777 120 % = 2.3010
6	LOD	0.7324 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Not reported	1.06 $\mu\text{g/mL}$
7	LOQ	2.2195 $\mu\text{g/mL}$	Not reported	3.21 $\mu\text{g/mL}$

The developed method employs a mobile phase consisting of Water: Acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) with 0.05 % TFA, which is simple and economical when compared with reported methods. This composition provided a sharp, symmetrical peak with a significantly shorter retention time (3.092 min), thereby reducing analysis time and solvent consumption. The developed method shows excellent linearity ($R^2 = 0.9999$), less retention time, lower LOD and LOQ, lower % RSD for precision and accuracy when compared to reported methods.

CONCLUSION

A simple, precise, and accurate RP-HPLC method was successfully developed and validated for the estimation of plecanatide in bulk and tablet dosage form. Method optimization was achieved using a simple mobile phase of water and acetonitrile (50:50 v/v) containing 0.05% TFA, with detection at 204 nm. Using a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min, the method produced a sharp and symmetric peak with a retention time of 3.092 min. Overall, the proposed method is accurate, reproducible, and stability-indicating, making it suitable for routine quality control and stability analysis of plecanatide in pharmaceutical formulations.

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All the authors have contributed equally.

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Declared none.

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